

Symmetric Crossed TX–RX Double-D Coil Structure

Parasitic Capacitance Reduction by Crossing Bridges
and Manufacturing by Nested Winding Prior to Forming

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Defensive Technical Publication – May 15, 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20211201](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20211201)

Symmetric crossed Double-D structure with opposed TX–RX separation bridges.

Abstract

This publication describes an electromagnetic Double-D coil structure intended in particular for metal detectors, pulse induction detectors, resonant square-wave systems, VLF architectures, and inductive measurement devices. The structure comprises a transmit coil and a receive coil arranged according to a general Double-D geometry, but configured in a crossed, complementary, and symmetric manner around a common mean plane.

In a first crossing region, the transmit coil locally passes above the receive coil. In a second crossing region, opposite or substantially symmetric with respect to the first one, the receive coil locally passes above the transmit coil. This alternation distributes the local vertical offsets between both coils and reduces electromagnetic imbalance caused by mechanical deformation, shocks, parasitic capacitance, local coupling variations, and manufacturing constraints.

The publication also describes an important aspect for square-wave detectors, fast-pulse detectors, and resonant excitation systems: the crossing bridges located respectively in the upper and lower parts of the Double-D structure allow the transmit and receive conductors to be locally separated. This controlled spacing reduces the direct parasitic capacitance between TX and RX, limits capacitive coupling from fast edges, and improves the stability of the transients measured on the receive channel.

The publication further describes a manufacturing process in which the two windings are first produced as nested closed loops, for example circular, oval, or elliptical loops, before being formed on a Double-D shaping jig. One coil may be wound inside or through the other by means of a shuttle-type winding device, analogous to systems used for winding toroidal cores, ribbons, or closed structures. After winding, flexible wires, for example Litz wire for the transmit coil and PTFE-insulated stranded wire for the receive coil, are shaped on a plastic jig, fixed by bonding or impregnation, and the temporary jig may then be removed.

This approach aims to obtain a Double-D coil that is electromagnetically balanced, mechanically reproducible, low in parasitic transmit-to-receive capacitance, and suitable for detection systems sensitive to small TX/RX imbalances.

Keywords: Double-D coil, metal detector, pulse induction, resonant square wave, crossed coil, symmetric coil, Litz wire, nested winding, induction balance, TX/RX coupling, parasitic capacitance, capacitive coupling, forming jig.

1 Technical Field

This publication relates to electromagnetic coil structures used in metal detectors, pulse induction detectors, square-wave detectors, VLF detectors, inductive sensors, and more generally systems using a coupled transmit coil and receive coil.

More specifically, it relates to so-called Double-D coils, in which a transmit coil and a receive coil each have an approximately semi-circular or D-shaped geometry, with a central overlap or proximity region intended to obtain a controlled induction balance.

Recent antenna structures for metal detectors describe non-coplanar transmit and receive coils, with a central overlap region and vertical offsets intended to improve induction balance under shock or mechanical deformation. The present document describes a different approach, based on a crossed, complementary, and symmetric distribution of the crossing regions, as well as on the intentional reduction of TX/RX parasitic capacitance in critical areas. French patent FR3168300A1 illustrates in particular an approach using non-coplanar coils and vertical offset in the central region, with overlap areas between transmit and receive coils.

2 Technical Problem

In a conventional Double-D coil, the central overlap region between the transmit coil and the receive coil is particularly critical. This region determines a large part of the direct coupling between the two coils, as well as the sensitivity of the system to mechanical variations.

The main problems encountered are the following:

- variation of direct transmit-to-receive coupling when the coil housing flexes;
- variation of induction balance under shock or torsion;
- sensitivity to height differences between the transmit-coil conductors and the receive-coil conductors;
- localized parasitic capacitance in the central region;
- capacitive injection of fast TX edges into the RX path;
- modification of receive transients in square-wave or fast-pulse detectors;
- mechanical microphony when the wires are not perfectly held;
- difficulty in producing several coils with identical electromagnetic response;
- imbalance caused by a non-symmetric crossing geometry between TX and RX conductors.

In high-dynamic-range detectors, in particular pulse induction detectors, resonant square-wave detectors, or systems using fast time-domain integration, these defects may produce receive errors, false signals, threshold variations, exaggerated ground effects, or loss of stability.

The capacitive problem is particularly important in systems with fast edges. A fast voltage transition on the TX coil can couple directly into the RX coil through the parasitic capacitance $C_{\text{TX-RX}}$ between conductors. The injected current can be approximated by:

$$i_C = C_{\text{TX-RX}} \frac{dV_{\text{TX}}}{dt} \quad (1)$$

Thus, even a small parasitic capacitance may produce a significant parasitic current when $\frac{dV_{\text{TX}}}{dt}$ is high. In a square-wave detector or resonant excitation system, this injection may mask or disturb the earliest part of the useful response.

3 General Principle of the Proposed Structure

The proposed structure comprises a transmit coil TX and a receive coil RX arranged according to a general Double-D geometry.

Unlike a structure in which one coil would be globally placed above the other, the two coils are here arranged in a crossed and complementary manner.

In a first crossing region, the transmit coil TX locally passes above the receive coil RX.

In a second crossing region, opposite or substantially symmetric with respect to a central axis of the coil, the receive coil RX locally passes above the transmit coil TX.

Thus, the two coils define a common mean plane, denoted P_m , around which the local vertical excursions of the wires are distributed in a complementary manner.

$$z_{\text{TX}}(x, y) - z_{\text{RX}}(x, y) \approx -[z_{\text{TX}}(-x, -y) - z_{\text{RX}}(-x, -y)] \quad (2)$$

This relation is not a strict geometrical constraint, but expresses the intended principle: spatial compensation of the relative vertical offsets between the two coils.

In addition to this geometrical compensation, the upper and lower crossing bridges physically separate the TX and RX conductors in regions where they would otherwise be close to each other. This local spacing contributes to reducing the direct parasitic capacitance between the two coils.

4 Reduction of TX/RX Parasitic Capacitance

In a conventional Double-D structure, the proximity of TX and RX conductors in the central region may create distributed parasitic capacitance. This capacitance can be represented, in simplified form, by an equivalent capacitance $C_{\text{TX-RX}}$ between the transmit coil and the receive coil.

For two nearby conductors or conductive surfaces, parasitic capacitance increases with the equivalent facing area and decreases when the dielectric distance increases. In simplified form:

$$C_{\text{par}} \approx \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \frac{S}{d} \quad (3)$$

where S represents an equivalent coupling area, d the distance between conductors, ε_0 the vacuum permittivity, and ε_r the relative permittivity of the insulating medium.

Although this expression is simplified and does not exactly describe a real pair of wires, it shows the essential physical principle: increasing the local spacing between TX and RX reduces parasitic capacitance.

In the proposed structure, the bridges located in the upper and lower parts of the Double-D structure do not only implement the geometrical crossing. They also impose a controlled local distance between the transmit and receive conductors.

This local distance reduces:

- direct parasitic capacitance between TX and RX;
- capacitive current injected into the RX path during fast TX edges;
- sensitivity to local dielectric variations;
- unwanted high-frequency coupling;
- parasitic transients at the beginning of receive windows;
- dependence of the induction balance on humidity, adhesives, resins, and nearby shielding materials.

In a square-wave detector, the parasitic capacitive current can be written as:

$$i_C(t) = C_{\text{TX-RX}} \frac{dV_{\text{TX}}(t)}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Reducing $C_{\text{TX-RX}}$ is therefore directly favorable to system stability, especially when voltage edges are steep or when the RX input stage has a high input impedance.

The parasitic voltage observed at the receiver then depends on the equivalent input impedance of the RX stage:

$$V_{\text{RX},C}(t) \approx Z_{\text{RX}}(t) \cdot C_{\text{TX-RX}} \frac{dV_{\text{TX}}(t)}{dt} \quad (5)$$

Reducing TX/RX parasitic capacitance therefore reduces the receive component that is not related to a metallic target or to an inductive ground response.

5 Particular Importance for Square-Wave and Resonant-Pulse Detectors

In a square-wave or resonant-pulse detector, the received signal waveform strongly depends on transient phenomena immediately after excitation or current inversion in the TX coil.

The TX coil may be subjected to fast voltage or current edges. These edges may couple into the RX path through several mechanisms:

- direct inductive coupling;
- direct capacitive coupling;
- coupling through electrostatic shielding;
- coupling through ground or nearby conductive structures;
- coupling through dielectric materials in the coil housing;
- microphonic coupling if the structure moves during the transient.

Inductive coupling can be reduced by geometrical and electromagnetic balancing. Capacitive coupling, however, requires particular attention to TX/RX spacing, facing surfaces, insulating materials, and bridge geometry.

The present structure acts on both mechanisms simultaneously:

1. through crossed symmetry, it distributes local inductive contributions;
2. through local conductor separation in the upper and lower bridges, it reduces TX/RX parasitic capacitance.

This combination is particularly suitable for detectors in which reception is performed in time windows close to TX excitation, since the earliest windows are the most sensitive to parasitic transients.

6 Intended Electromagnetic Advantage

The direct coupling between the transmit coil and the receive coil can be represented, in simplified form, by a mutual inductance M :

$$M = \frac{\Phi_{\text{RX}}}{I_{\text{TX}}} \quad (6)$$

where Φ_{RX} is the magnetic flux coupled into the receive coil and I_{TX} is the current flowing through the transmit coil.

In a Double-D coil, the objective is not necessarily to maximize M , but to finely control its value in order to obtain a stable induction balance.

A local mechanical disturbance can modify the relative distance between the TX and RX conductors, causing a local coupling variation:

$$\Delta M \approx \frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \Delta z \quad (7)$$

In a non-symmetric structure, local contributions may add together and produce a significant global variation of the balance.

In the proposed structure, the complementary vertical crossings tend to distribute local variations with opposite signs, which may reduce the global first-order contribution:

$$\int_S \Delta M(x, y) dS \rightarrow \text{reduced value by spatial compensation} \quad (8)$$

This compensation is not perfect under all conditions, because it depends on the exact geometry, the local field, the wire position, the frequency, parasitic capacitances, and the mechanical response of the support. Nevertheless, it constitutes a robust design principle for reducing imbalance effects induced by global deformation.

The intended advantage is therefore not only improved inductive balance, but a combined reduction:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta M \rightarrow \text{reduced by geometrical symmetry} \\ C_{\text{TX-RX}} \rightarrow \text{reduced by local TX/RX spacing} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

7 Geometrical Description

The coil comprises two main lobes forming a Double-D geometry.

The transmit coil TX may predominantly occupy a first half of the structure, while the receive coil RX predominantly occupies the complementary half.

The two coils cross in at least two crossing regions. These regions are preferably arranged in an opposite or symmetric manner with respect to the geometrical center of the coil.

In a first region, referred to as the TX upper bridge region, the conductor of the transmit coil passes above the conductor of the receive coil.

In a second region, referred to as the RX upper bridge region, the conductor of the receive coil passes above the conductor of the transmit coil.

The bridges may be formed by progressive bends, controlled local elevations, or guiding channels molded into a temporary or permanent support.

The bridges may also be designed to impose a minimum distance d_{TXRX} between the TX and RX conductors:

$$d_{\text{TXRX}} \geq d_{\text{min}} \tag{10}$$

This minimum distance may be selected according to:

- the TX voltage;
- the edge speed;
- the admissible parasitic capacitance;
- the required mechanical stiffness;
- the dielectric constant of the material between conductors;
- the available thickness inside the coil housing;
- the minimum bending radius of the wires.

8 Schematic Top-View Illustration

The following figure presents a representation derived from the geometrical model of the proposed structure. It illustrates the general top view of the symmetric crossed Double-D coil, as well as the two opposed crossing regions.

It can be observed that, in a first bridge region, the receive coil RX passes above the transmit coil TX, whereas, in a second opposed region, the transmit coil TX passes above the receive coil RX. This alternating crossing contributes to the global symmetry of the structure and also increases the local distance between conductors, thereby contributing to the reduction of the parasitic capacitance C_{TX-RX} between the two coils.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the symmetric crossed TX–RX Double-D structure. The general view shows the organization of the two loops, while the detail insets highlight the two opposed bridges: in the first one, RX passes above TX, and in the second one, TX passes above RX. These bridges implement the complementary crossing and impose local spacing between conductors, which is favorable to reducing parasitic capacitance between transmit and receive coils.

9 Details of the Vertical Crossing Regions

The two crossing regions are important elements of the proposed structure. They provide both the complementary geometrical crossing of the windings and the local spacing between the TX and RX conductors.

In the first region, the receive coil RX locally passes above the transmit coil TX. In the second region, located in an opposite or substantially symmetric position, the transmit coil TX locally passes above the receive coil RX.

This controlled inversion of the relative vertical position distributes the height offsets between the two coils around a common mean plane. It also increases the local dielectric distance between conductors, thereby contributing to the reduction of parasitic capacitance $C_{\text{TX-RX}}$.

Figure 2: Three-dimensional details of the two opposed crossing regions. Each bridge imposes a local separation between the transmit and receive conductors. This separation reduces direct capacitive coupling while preserving a crossed and symmetric Double-D structure.

10 Manufacturing Process

The structure may be manufactured according to a process comprising the following steps.

10.1 Step 1: Winding of Nested Loops

The transmit coil and the receive coil are first produced as two nested closed loops.

These loops may be:

- circular;
- oval;
- elliptical;
- pseudo-circular;
- polygonal with rounded corners;
- or any other initial shape that is easier to wind than the final Double-D shape.

One of the coils may be wound inside the other, or partially through the other, by means of a shuttle-type winding device.

Such a device may be inspired by winding machines used for toroidal cores, closed coils, ribbons, special sensors, or structures in which the wire must pass through an already formed loop.

10.2 Step 2: Use of Flexible Wires

The transmit coil may be made from Litz wire, for example with a number of strands ranging from a few strands to several tens of strands, or even around sixty strands or more, depending on frequency, current, and allowable resistance.

Litz wire provides several advantages:

- high mechanical flexibility;
- good formability;
- reduction of skin-effect-related losses in certain frequency ranges;
- better current distribution among strands;
- good tolerance to moderate bending cycles during manufacturing.

The receive coil may be made from PTFE-insulated stranded wire, i.e. with a Teflon-type insulation. This type of wire provides excellent flexibility, good dielectric stability, good thermal resistance, and low sensitivity to forming constraints.

The use of highly flexible wires allows an initially circular or oval shape to be transformed into a final Double-D geometry without imposing excessive mechanical stress on the conductors.

10.3 Step 3: Forming on a Plastic Jig

After winding, the two nested loops are placed on a forming jig.

This jig may be made of plastic, machined polymer, 3D-printed material, composite material, or any electrically insulating and mechanically stable material.

The jig imposes:

- the external shape of the coil housing;
- the Double-D geometry;
- the position of the central region;
- the bending radius of the wires;
- the relative TX/RX position;
- the local height of the crossing bridges;
- the local spacing between TX and RX in the bridge regions;
- the maximum admissible parasitic capacitance between transmit and receive coils.

The jig may be temporary. In such a case, it is used only during the forming and fixing step, and is then removed after bonding, impregnation, or polymerization.

10.4 Step 4: Local Jigs for the Bridges

The regions where one wire passes above the other may be formed using small local jigs.

These local jigs define:

- the bridge height;
- the upward and downward slope of the wire;
- the minimum bending radius;
- the dielectric distance between conductors;
- the geometrical repeatability of the crossing;
- the local reduction of TX/RX parasitic capacitance;
- the minimum spacing d_{TXRX} between the wires.

The bridge should not form a sharp angle. A progressive transition is preferable in order to limit mechanical stress, prevent later wire displacement, and reduce local variations in parasitic capacitance.

The local jig may therefore be designed not only as a mechanical crossing tool, but also as an electromagnetic and capacitive control element.

10.5 Step 5: Bonding, Impregnation, or Immobilization

Once the wires are positioned, they may be fixed by:

- local bonding;
- resin impregnation;
- silicone deposition;
- flexible epoxy resin;
- impregnation varnish;
- structural foam;
- mechanical retention in a molded groove.

The choice of the fixing material depends on frequency, voltage level, required dielectric stability, thermal resistance, allowable mass, microphonic sensitivity of the system, and admissible parasitic capacitance.

After polymerization or mechanical stabilization, the temporary jig may be removed if necessary.

11 Illustration of the Manufacturing Process

The following figure summarizes the proposed manufacturing process in three steps.

In a first step, the two windings are produced as nested closed loops, for example circular, oval, or quasi-circular loops, allowing one coil to pass inside the other.

In a second step, the two loops are progressively formed on a Double-D type jig. This operation produces the intended general geometry as well as the two opposed crossing regions.

In a third step, the final geometry is stabilized by bonding, impregnation, or retention in a suitable mechanical structure, in order to preserve the global symmetry and the local conductor spacing in the bridge regions.

(a) Initial winding of two nested closed loops.

(b) Progressive forming on a Double-D type jig.

(c) Final geometry with opposed bridges and symmetric crossing.

Figure 3: Illustration of the manufacturing process of the proposed structure. Left: initial winding as nested loops. Center: forming on a Double-D jig. Right: stabilized final geometry, including two opposed bridges that provide complementary crossing of the windings and local spacing favorable to the reduction of parasitic capacitance C_{TX-RX} .

12 Embodiment Variants

The described structure may be adapted in many ways without departing from the general principle.

12.1 Shape Variants

The final shape may be:

- circular Double-D;
- elliptical Double-D;
- oval Double-D;
- rectangular with rounded corners;
- butterfly-shaped;
- pseudo-Double-D;
- intentionally asymmetric to compensate for a specific response of the ground, shielding, or parasitic capacitance.

12.2 Crossing Variants

The number of crossings may be:

- two main crossings;
- four symmetrically distributed crossings;
- several low-height crossings;
- a progressive crossing distributed over a long region;
- a periodic alternation of TX/RX passages.

12.3 Capacitive Variants

The reduction of parasitic capacitance may be obtained or reinforced by:

- local vertical spacing between TX and RX;
- local lateral spacing between TX and RX;
- reduction of the length of nearby parallel conductors;
- different conductor orientation in the bridge regions;

- use of an insulator with low dielectric constant;
- addition of a dielectric spacer;
- optimization of the electrostatic shield;
- limitation of facing conductive surfaces.

12.4 Material Variants

The conductors may be:

- Litz wire;
- stranded copper wire;
- silver-plated wire;
- PTFE-insulated wire;
- flexible enamelled wire;
- conductive ribbon;
- flexible printed conductor;
- hybrid wire/trace conductor.

12.5 Fixing Variants

The wires may be fixed:

- in a molded groove;
- by spot bonding;
- by complete resin encapsulation;
- by vacuum impregnation;
- by retaining foam;
- by insulating adhesive film;
- by overmolding.

13 Application to Resonant Square-Wave Detectors

In a resonant square-wave detector, the transmit coil may be excited by an alternating or pseudo-alternating current sequence, with fast transitions, resonance phases, acquisition windows, and time-domain observation periods.

In this context, the stability of the geometrical relationship between TX and RX is particularly important.

A local coupling variation may produce:

- a variation of TX residual signal in the RX path;
- a shift of the balance point;
- a modification of the early-window response;
- a displacement of the audio threshold;
- an increase in false signals during coil movement;
- increased sensitivity to shocks;
- stronger capacitive injection during TX edges.

The proposed symmetric crossed structure is therefore particularly suitable for a system in which the RX response is measured in precise time windows after TX excitation.

In a square-wave system, TX/RX parasitic capacitance can become a determining parameter, sometimes as critical as residual mutual inductance. Reducing this capacitance improves RX signal cleanliness, reduces edge disturbances, and facilitates exploitation of early receive windows.

The structure may also be combined with:

- analog offset compensation;
- hardware time-domain integration;
- digital balance compensation;
- differential measurement;
- multi-window acquisition;
- time-constant classification;
- vector analysis of ground response.

14 Application to Pulse Induction Detectors

In a pulse induction detector, the transmit coil generates a transient magnetic field and the receive coil measures the induced decay after current cutoff or reversal.

The proposed structure may be used with:

- monopolar pulses;
- bipolar pulses;
- H-bridges;
- positive and negative sequences;
- multiple integration windows;
- floating differential systems;
- induction-balance architectures.

The symmetric crossed geometry can reduce direct coupling disturbances and improve the stability of receive windows, especially when the coil is subjected to bending, mechanical pressure, vibration, or temperature variation.

In fast-edge architectures, the reduction of TX/RX parasitic capacitance can also reduce the amplitude of parasitic impulses injected at the moment of current cutoff or reversal.

15 Physical Limits and Precautions

The proposed structure does not eliminate all coupling problems between TX and RX. It reduces certain contributions by symmetry and local spacing, but it does not guarantee perfect cancellation.

The main limitations are:

- real geometrical imperfections of the bridges;
- variations in spacing between turns;
- parasitic capacitance between superposed conductors;
- proximity between crossing regions and the sensitive central region;
- dielectric variations caused by adhesives, resins, or plastics;
- influence of the electrostatic shield of the coil housing;
- frequency dependence of wire impedance;
- residual microphony if bonding is insufficient;
- repeatability of the forming process;
- the possibility that excessive spacing locally modifies the inductive balance.

For these reasons, it is preferable that the bridges be made with progressive bending radii, controlled height, sufficient dielectric spacing, and stable mechanical retention.

It is also preferable to measure, after manufacturing:

- TX coil inductance;
- RX coil inductance;
- series resistance;
- TX/RX parasitic capacitance;
- residual mutual inductance;
- balance variation under bending;
- balance variation under shock;
- thermal response;
- stability after impregnation.

16 Recommended Experimental Characterization

In order to objectively evaluate the interest of the structure, it is recommended to compare at least two coils:

1. a conventional Double-D coil;
2. a symmetric crossed Double-D coil according to the present publication.

Measurements may include:

- measurement of TX/RX coupling in free air;
- measurement of TX/RX parasitic capacitance;
- measurement of capacitive current injected during a TX edge;
- measurement of RX residual signal after TX excitation;
- measurement of signal variation under controlled bending;
- measurement of signal variation under vibration;
- measurement of variation with temperature;
- measurement of response to a conductive target;
- measurement of response to magnetic ground;
- measurement of response to ferrite or magnetic rock;
- comparison of audio or digital noise during movement.

A simple metric can be defined as:

$$S_{\text{meca}} = \frac{|V_{\text{RX,bending}} - V_{\text{RX,rest}}|}{|V_{\text{RX,target}} - V_{\text{RX,rest}}|} \quad (11)$$

where S_{meca} represents the relative sensitivity to mechanical deformation, $V_{\text{RX,bending}}$ the voltage measured under mechanical constraint, $V_{\text{RX,rest}}$ the rest voltage, and $V_{\text{RX,target}}$ the voltage obtained with a reference target.

A lower value of S_{meca} indicates better relative mechanical stability.

A second metric may be defined for capacitive coupling:

$$S_{\text{cap}} = \frac{|V_{\text{RX,edge}}|}{\left| \frac{dV_{\text{TX}}}{dt} \right|} \quad (12)$$

where $V_{\text{RX,edge}}$ represents the parasitic voltage observed on the RX path at the moment of a TX edge. A lower value of S_{cap} indicates better immunity to capacitive coupling.

17 Distinctive Elements of the Present Publication

The described structure is distinguished by the combination of the following elements:

1. a general Double-D geometry;
2. a crossed transmit coil and receive coil;
3. a complementary alternation of vertical passages;
4. a local bridge where TX passes above RX;
5. an opposite or symmetric bridge where RX passes above TX;
6. a common mean plane around which the vertical excursions are distributed;
7. a search for global electromagnetic symmetry;
8. a local reduction of TX/RX parasitic capacitance by controlled spacing of the conductors;
9. a reduction of capacitive coupling associated with fast edges in square-wave or pulse systems;
10. an initial winding process in the form of nested loops;
11. subsequent forming on a Double-D jig;
12. possible use of highly flexible wires, such as Litz wire for TX and PTFE-insulated stranded wire for RX;
13. use of local jigs to form the bridges;
14. final fixing by bonding, impregnation, molded groove, or resin.

The central element is therefore not only the fact that one coil locally passes above another, but the complementary and symmetric distribution of these passages, associated with local TX/RX spacing intended to reduce parasitic capacitance, and with a manufacturing process allowing the structure to be produced reproducibly.

18 Example Embodiment

In one example embodiment, the transmit coil is made from flexible Litz wire comprising several tens of strands. The receive coil is made from PTFE-insulated stranded wire.

The two coils are first wound as nested circular loops. The RX loop is placed inside or through the TX loop. A shuttle-type winding machine allows the wire to pass through the opening formed by the already produced loop.

The two loops are then placed in a detection coil housing comprising a temporary plastic forming jig. This jig progressively imposes a Double-D shape on the two coils.

In the upper part of the central region, the jig imposes a local bridge in which the TX conductor passes above the RX conductor. In the lower part of the central region, a second bridge imposes the inverse configuration, in which the RX conductor passes above the TX conductor.

These two bridges are designed to produce a controlled local distance between TX and RX, in order to reduce the parasitic capacitance between the two coils. This reduction is particularly useful when the TX coil is driven by fast edges, as in a square-wave detector or in a resonant-pulse system.

After placement, the conductors are bonded or impregnated. The temporary jig is then removed, or left in place if it is part of the final mechanical structure.

The resulting coil has a crossed, symmetric Double-D structure that is mechanically stabilized and has reduced TX/RX parasitic capacitance.

19 Possible Applications

The structure may be used in:

- VLF metal detectors;
- pulse induction metal detectors;
- square-wave detectors;
- resonant square-wave detectors;
- H-bridge systems;
- bipolar transmit systems;
- fast-edge systems;
- industrial inductive sensors;
- proximity sensors;
- conductivity measurement systems;
- magnetic susceptibility measurement systems;
- material characterization devices.

20 Conclusion

This publication describes a Double-D coil structure in which the transmit coil and the receive coil are crossed in a complementary and symmetric manner.

The principle consists in distributing the vertical crossings between the two coils, so that the transmit coil locally passes above the receive coil in a first region, while the receive coil locally passes above the transmit coil in an opposite or symmetric region.

This organization defines a common mean plane and can reduce certain electromagnetic imbalances caused by mechanical deformation, shocks, local coupling variations, and parasitic capacitance.

An essential aspect of this structure is that the upper and lower crossing bridges also locally separate the TX and RX conductors. This spacing reduces parasitic capacitance between transmit and receive coils, which is particularly favorable for square-wave detectors, resonant-pulse systems, and fast-edge architectures.

The publication also describes a manufacturing process in which the two coils are first produced as nested loops, then formed on a Double-D jig. The use of flexible wires, such as Litz wire for transmission and PTFE-insulated stranded wire for reception, facilitates this forming process without excessive mechanical stress.

Overall, the proposed approach is intended to improve stability, reproducibility, electromagnetic symmetry, and capacitive cleanliness of Double-D coils used in inductive detection systems.

Defensive Publication Statement

The content of this document is intended to make public a Double-D coil architecture with symmetric crossed windings, as well as an associated manufacturing process based on nested winding prior to forming.

This publication also makes public the use of upper and lower crossing bridges as a means for locally separating TX and RX conductors in order to reduce parasitic capacitance between transmission and reception, in particular in square-wave, fast-pulse, or resonant-excitation detectors.

The geometrical, material, and procedural variants described herein are to be understood as non-limiting examples allowing a person skilled in the art to reproduce or adapt the general principle.

Citation

TARTAR, Alexandre. *Symmetric Crossed TX–RX Double-D Coil Structure: Parasitic Capacitance Reduction by Crossing Bridges and Manufacturing by Nested Winding Prior to Forming*. Defensive Technical Publication, 2026. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20211201](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20211201).

BibTeX

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@misc{tartar2026crossedddcoil,  
  author      = {TARTAR, Alexandre},  
  title       = {Symmetric Crossed TX--RX Double-D Coil Structure:  
                Parasitic Capacitance Reduction by Crossing Bridges  
                and Manufacturing by Nested Winding Prior to Forming},  
  year        = {2026},  
  publisher   = {Zenodo},  
  doi         = {10.5281/zenodo.20211201},  
  url         = {https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20211201},  
  note        = {Defensive Technical Publication}  
}
```